

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF COMMUNICATION AND LANGUAGE SOCIALIZATION IN ONLINE MULTIPLAYER GAMES

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Abstract. *The communicative processes and specific features of language socialization that occur in online multiplayer games (Massively Multiplayer Online Games – MMO) are analyzed.*

The study covers the communicative relationships formed in the virtual environment, linguistic cooperation between players, the use of jargon and slang, as well as the impact of online games on the speech and socialization of young people. The article argues that online games are not only an entertainment tool, but also an important social platform for language learning, the development of communicative competence, and the formation of intercultural communication.

Keywords: *Online games, language socialization, communication, virtual community, gamers' speech, internet linguistics, MMO games, intercultural communication, digital communication, language environment.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ КОММУНИКАЦИИ И ЯЗЫКОВОЙ СОЦИАЛИЗАЦИИ В МНОГОПОЛЬЗОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ ОНЛАЙН-ИГРАХ

Аннотация. *В статье анализируются коммуникативные процессы и специфические особенности языковой социализации, происходящие в многопользовательских онлайн-играх (ММО). Рассматриваются коммуникативные отношения, формирующиеся в виртуальной среде, языковое сотрудничество между игроками, использование жаргона и сленга, а также влияние онлайн-игр на речь и социализацию молодежи. В статье утверждается, что онлайн-игры являются не только развлекательным инструментом, но и важной социальной платформой для изучения языка, развития коммуникативной компетенции и формирования межкультурной коммуникации.*

Ключевые слова: *Онлайн-игры, языковая социализация, коммуникация, виртуальное сообщество, речь игроков, интернет-лингвистика, ММО-игры, межкультурная коммуникация, цифровая коммуникация, языковая среда.*

ONLAYN KO'P O'YINCHILI O'YINLARDA MULOQOT VA TIL IJTIMOIYLASHUVINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI

Annotatsiya. *Onlayn ko'p o'yinchili o'yinlarda (Massively Multiplayer Online Games– MMO) yuzaga keladigan muloqot jarayonlari hamda til ijtimoiylashuvining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda virtual muhitda shakllanadigan kommunikativ munosabatlar, o'yinchilar o'rtasidagi lingvistik hamkorlik, jargon va slanglarning qo'llanilishi, shuningdek, onlayn o'yinlarning yoshlar nutqi va ijtimoiylashuviga ta'siri yoritilgan. Maqolada onlayn o'yinlar nafaqat ko'ngilochar vosita, balki til o'rganish, kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish va madaniyatlararo muloqotni shakllantiruvchi muhim ijtimoiy platforma ekanligi asoslab berilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Onlayn o'yinlar, til ijtimoiylashuvi, kommunikatsiya, virtual hamjamiyat, geymerlar nutqi, internet lingvistikasi, MMO o'yinlar, madaniyatlararo muloqot, raqamli kommunikatsiya, til muhiti.*

Introduction

The 21st century, as the century of information technologies, has a significant impact on all aspects of human life. In particular, as a result of the development of Internet technologies, new forms of virtual communication have emerged, which have begun to play an important role in people's daily communicative activities. In this process, online multiplayer games have become not only a means of entertainment, but also a social space that unites millions of users.

Today, games such as PUBG Mobile, Mobile Legends, Free Fire, Data 2, League of Legends, Fortnite, World of Warcraft unite people from different countries of the world in a single virtual space, providing regular communication and cooperation between them. During the game, participants exchange ideas through text chat, voice communication, emoji and other communicative means. As a result, a unique language environment is formed in virtual communities.

Language socialization refers to the process of a person's assimilation of the language norms, communicative rules and speech behavior of a particular society. Traditionally, this process was carried out through the family, school, peer group and media, but today the Internet and online games are also becoming important agents of socialization. Young people participating in online games, as they communicate with representatives of different countries, acquire new words, phrases, jargon and communicative strategies. This not only expands their language competence, but also serves to form a global communicative culture. Therefore, studying the specific aspects of communication and language socialization in online games is one of the current issues for modern linguistics, sociolinguistics and pedagogy. Communication in online multiplayer games is carried out in 3 different ways, and these include text communication, voice communication and visual communication. Nowadays, online games have become not only an entertainment tool, but also an important platform for developing communication between people.

In particular, in multiplayer games, people from different parts of the world work together as a team, exchanging ideas and cooperating. This process has a great impact on language socialization. During the game, participants communicate through text chat, voice chat or various symbols. As a result, they learn new words, phrases and slang. Especially since English is widely used in online games, many players naturally acquire foreign words and terms. Online games also develop the communication skills of young people. To win in team games, players need to communicate with each other quickly and clearly. This strengthens their ability to express ideas fluently, listen and cooperate. The virtual gaming environment also brings together representatives of different nationalities and cultures. Players get to know each other's culture, customs and speech styles. As a result, intercultural communication develops, and people develop a sense of tolerance and mutual respect. However, the impact of online games on language is not limited to positive aspects. In some cases, excessive use of foreign words or the popularization of Internet

jargon can affect the literary norms of the native language. Therefore, it is important to use games wisely and preserve language culture. In general, online multiplayer games create new forms of communication, language learning and socialization in modern society, making a significant contribution to the communicative and social development of young people.

Distinctive features of the language socialization process: Language socialization in the online gaming environment consists of 3 directions.

First, players master new linguistic units. Terms and jargon that are often used during the game gradually enter everyday speech.

Second, a process of communicative adaptation is observed. When a new player joins a community, he is forced to learn the speech norms adopted by the group. This process is an important form of socialization.

Third, players improve their speech strategies. Since success in team games often depends on effective communication, participants try to express their thoughts clearly and intelligibly.

In conclusion, Online multiplayer games have become an important communicative space of modern digital society. The communication processes taking shape in this environment are giving rise to new forms of language socialization. Text and voice communication between players, the use of special jargon, international communication, and the creation of virtual communities are The formation of language has a direct impact on language development.

The results of the study show that online games play an important role in developing the communicative competence of young people, learning foreign languages, and strengthening intercultural dialogue. At the same time, the widespread use of Internet jargon and the active use of foreign language elements also have a certain impact on national language standards. In the future, a more in-depth study of the linguistic, psychological, and pedagogical aspects of language socialization in the environment of online games is one of the urgent tasks facing modern science.

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